

Impresso Datalab: Embedding Newspapers for Multimodal and Multilingual Data Analysis

To better support researchers and their evolving research practices, cultural heritage institutions are actively experimenting with data labs to offer access to computational tools and datasets. Against this background, the proposed workshop will explore novel opportunities for the exploration of digital cultural heritage collections, through semantic search across languages and modalities based on embeddings and vector representations.

This workshop is organised by the interdisciplinary research project Impresso - Media Monitoring of the Past (<https://impresso-project.ch/>). Participants will experiment with different corpus creation methodologies and search methods using keywords, images captions, metadata, semantic enrichments and embeddings to retrieve documents from large-scale newspapers collections (articles, advertisements, images, etc.).

Some of the questions to be explored in this session are:

- How can we advance exploration of cultural heritage collections with AI-tools?
- To what extent do such tools and approaches affect research practices and the way we navigate large-scale and diverse data sources?
- What are the potentials and limitations of such methods?

The workshop will be structured as follows:

09:30-10:00: Introduction to Impresso Web App & Datalab

10:30-11:00: Exploring search methods with Impresso Web App & Datalab

11:00-11:30: Break

11:30-12:30: Conversation on potentials and limitations of current search methods

12:30-13:30: Lunch

13:30-14:00: Introduction to embeddings

14:00-15:30: Exploring search potential with embeddings via Web App & Datalab

15:30-16:00: Break

16:00-17:00: Final discussion on the value of embeddings for navigating digitised collections